

N-t-Butyl Thiocarbamoyl N'-Guanyl Hydrazine and its Metal Complexes

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A study of N-t-butyl thiocarbamoyl N'-guanyl hydrazine as complexing ligand and its Ni, Cu(II), Zn, Pd(II) and Cd complexes is described. The ligand is monobasic and forms 1:2 complexes. Bonding in nickel complex is different from the rest. Ultraviolet, visible and i.r. spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes and magnetic properties of the latter are discussed.

Authors have studied^{1,2} a series of ligands of the general formula

Earlier³⁻⁵, ligand with another thiocarbamoyl group in place of the carbamoyl group has been studied. Authors also have studied a ligand in which a phenyl-guanyl group replaces the carbamoyl group⁶. The present ligand has the following configuration.

(BTGH or LH)

The present communication describes Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Palladium(II) complexes of the ligand and some of their physical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Physical measurements and other experimental details were same as described in our previous communication.

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Preparation of ligand: The ligand was prepared as *p*-toluene sulphonate by the method of Kurzer⁷ and was purified by the same method described⁷. The ligand as *p*-toluene sulphonate (M.P. 195°) is highly soluble in ethanol, less soluble in cold water, sparingly soluble in heptane and insoluble in ether.

Preparation of complexes: Complexes are prepared by the following two methods:

1. Metal salt (0.001 mole) and ligand (0.004 mole) were dissolved in water ethanol mixture separately and the two solutions mixed together. The mixture was kept on a water bath and the pH of the solution raised to ~ 8 by adding sodium bicarbonate solution drop by drop and stirred thoroughly. The desired precipitate was obtained after digestion on water bath for a while. The complex was purified by several decantation washing and crystallised from methanol. This method is applicable for nickel and zinc complexes only.

2. Metal salt (0.001 mole) was dissolved in excess ammonia and mixed with ligand (0.004 mole) previously dissolved in water-ethanol mixture and stirred thoroughly. The crystalline precipitate formed was thoroughly washed with water. All the complexes are prepared by this way.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is apparent from Table 1 that the ligand is monobasic and forms neutral complexes of the type ML_2 . The ligand essentially consists of thiourea and a guanidine unit. The u-v spectra (Table 2) show a little delocalisation between the thiourea and guanidine unit

TABLE I

Analysis^a data of the N-t-butyl thiocarbamoyl N'-guanyl hydrazine PTS and its metal complexes

Compound	Colour	Metal	Nitrogen	Sulphur	μ_{eff}
NiL ₂	Grey	13.57	32.32	14.76	†
		(13.51)	(32.21)	(14.72)	
CuL ₂	Black	14.44	31.78	14.39	1.86
		(14.47)	(31.85)	(14.56)	
ZnL ₂	White	14.30	31.63	14.48	
		(14.81)	(31.72)	(14.50)	
PdL ₂	Rose red	21.74	28.92	13.16	
		(22.11)	(29.00)	(13.26)	
CdL ₂	White	22.61	28.14	13.02	
		(22.96)	(28.66)	(13.10)	
LH*	White		19.09	17.67	
			(19.41)	(17.78)	

^a Figures in parentheses are the required percentages.

* Here the ligand as *p*-toluene sulphonate.

† It denotes the diamagnetic character.

TABLE 2

U.V. spectral data of t-BTGH-PTS and its metal complexes

Compound	Medium	λ_{max} (nm)	Frequency (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{max}
LH-PTS	Water pH = 1.1	207 sh	48309	27600
		220 sh	45455	23830
		248	40323	14825
	pH = 4.1	210	47619	17539
		220 sh	45455	16577
		248	40323	11027
	pH = 9.8	220	45455	23608
		260	38462	8288
		Methanol	217	46088
		255	39216	10773
	NiL ₂	214	46729	23150
		248	40323	27933
280		35714	16711	
ZnL ₂	Ethanol	217	46083	25943
		270	37037	22911
		290	34483	10613
PdL ₂		212	47170	26550
		232	43103	39600
		262	38168	21600
CdL ₂	Methanol	209	47847	23664
		267	37453	16638
		295	33898	5776

as in our previous communication^{2,6}. By analogy with guanidines⁸, the guanidine unit of the ligand may be assumed to be protonated in acidic and aqueous solution and deprotonated in methanol and in aqueous solution, at higher pH. The band at 255 nm of deprotonated ligand undergoes hypsochromic shift on protonation. In alkaline solution, the C = S group is assumed to be enolised (at least partly as the buffering action of the ligand may prevent complete enolisation and ionisation) On the basis of the positions of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ bands the complexes can be divided into two groups from this u.v. spectra—zinc, cadmium and palladium belong to the first and nickel to the second. It is not possible to take u.v. spectra of copper complex as the complex becomes turbid rapidly in the available solvents. In the first group there is $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band at 260 ~ 270 nm. Nickel complex of the second

group shows $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band at 248 nm, almost the expected position of the non-enolised thiourea unit. This observation is similar to our previous work⁶. It seems, therefore, that zinc, cadmium and palladium are linked with sulphur in the enolised form and nickel, if linked at all, with non-enolised form of the group concerned in the respective complex. There is no indication that guanylyl *N* is valency linked. The only thing is that composition states a valency link. Therefore, if *S* is not involved, presumably, the guanylyl *N* is involved.

TABLE 3

I.R. spectra of t-BTGH-PTS and its metal complexes (in KBr)

L-PTS	NiL ₂	CuL ₂	ZnL ₂	PdL ₂	CdL ₂
1675 s				1675 sh	1655 sh
1647 sh	1634 s		1635 sh	1635 s	1637 s
1640 s	1610 s	1621 s	1615 sh	1625 s	1618 sh
			1602 s	1617 sh	1610 ms
1596 w	1587 sh			1582 s	
	1582 sh	1575 s		1576 s	1575 sh
		1570 sh		1571 sh	1567 sh
	1565 s	1565 sh		1566 sh	1563 sh
	1555 sh	1555 sh			1558 s
1540 m		1545 sh	1545 sh	1545 sh	1548 s
1534 m	1534 sh	1537 sh	1540 sh		1531 sh
			1535 sh		
1500 sh	1502	1523 sh	1528 vs		
1491 w		1488 sh		1490 m	
1477 w	1471 shb	1475 m			
1441 mw	1460 s	1445 m	1450 ms	1450 m	1461 m
	1449 sh		1440 ms		1440 m
	1447 s		1419 ms		
1395 sh	1399 w				
1381 sh	1372 m	1380 w		1388 w	1371 w
1375 m	1359 m	1361 sh	1354 mw	1357 mw	
1351 m	1339 m	1325 vwb	1336 mw		1345 mw
1298 w					
1270 mw	1258 m	1254 m		1258 m	1240 m
1195 s	1212 m	1213 m	1219 m	1215 mw	1205 wm
			1185 m		
1157 s	1149 w	1150 w	1137 wm	1150 w	1150 vw
1120 s	1111 wb			1090 wb	1145 wm
	1064 wb		1050 w	1055 w	
1002 s	1031 w		1015 vw	1030 w	
			997 w	1005 w	985 q
			920 vw	935 wb	
840 w	840 vw	834 w		837 w	875 wb
818 w			810 wm		820 w
795 w					
755 wm	757 w	760 w	745 w	765 w	755 w
700 wm					
678 m					

I.R. spectra (Table 3) are very complex. However, some information can be obtained certainly. The ligand shows strong bands at 1675 and 1002 cm^{-1} . The band at 1675 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to $\nu(\text{NCN})^9$ and $\nu(\text{CN})^9$ and at 1002 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{NCN})^9$ for the guanidine unit of the protonated ligand. These bands are weakened and lowered in all complexes. This indicates that the guanyl nitrogen is involved either in coordination or in valency link. The band observed at 1640 cm^{-1} in the ligand may be assigned to NH_2 bending frequency¹⁰. This band remains almost unaltered in frequency on coordination. The band at 1540 cm^{-1} of the ligand may be explained, as the amide II band *i.e.*, NH deformation plus CN anti-symmetric stretching. On coordination the frequency is increased by about 30 ~ 35 cm^{-1} in Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II). In Zn(II), there is a band of this type but it is very much weakened. In Cd there is no appreciable change of the same band. The band at 1375 cm^{-1} ¹⁰ of the ligand which arises from a vibration consisting of NH_2 rocking, CN symmetric stretching and $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$ stretching motions remain practically unaltered in frequency in Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) and Cd(II) complexes. In Cu(II), Pd(II) and Cd(II) complexes this band is weakened and in Zn(II) the frequency is lowered by about 20 cm^{-1} . It is evident from the NH_2 bending, amide II and $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$ bands position in the complexes that Zn and Cd are isolated from other complexes in coordination. The bands observed in the ligand at 1195, 1157, 1120, 1020, 805 and 678 cm^{-1} are due to *p*-toluene sulphonic acid.

Nickel and palladium complexes are diamagnetic. Copper complex shows paramagnetism. Spectra (Table 4) of nickel and palladium complexes are independent of solvent and that of copper complex is dependent. The spectra are very broad. The excess ligand has little effect on the complexes. The spectra, however, do not suggest any stereochemistry quantitatively but there is an indication of the planar configuration of the complexes. In

TABLE 4

Visible spectra of metal complexes of t-BTGH

Compound	Medium	λ_{max} (nm)	Frequency (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{max}
NiL ₂	Methanol	630	15873	137
„ +L	„	630	15873	139
NiL ₂	Pyridine	650	15385	104
„ +L	„	520	19231	157
		660 (Broad)	15152	71
CuL ₂	Pyridine	No bands		
„ +L	„	460	21739	370
PdL ₂	Ethanol	500	20000	246
„ +L	„	495	20202	250
PdL ₂	Pyridine	500	20000	253
„ +L	„	495	20202	258
PdL ₂	Nitrobenzene	500	20000	441
„ +L	„	500	20000	445

the visible region only $d \rightarrow d$ transition are observed. The visible spectra of these complexes are similar to those of N thiocarbonyl N' carbonyl hydrazine and its derivatives described earlier. From the positions of composite bands it appears that both the types of ligands offer similar ligand strength, although without the solid state spectra and gaussian analysis of the bands proper evaluation of ligand strength is not possible.

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